

Identifying Nature’s Largest Telescopes with the AbacusSummit N-body Simulations

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ABSTRACT

Instances of strong gravitational lensing create unique opportunities to study ultra-high-redshift galaxies and dark matter distributions with greater granularity than otherwise possible. Strong lensing is typically observed during the chance alignment of two galaxy clusters along the line of sight, which are uncommon and unpredictable scenarios. However, a projection along the cosmic web could be commonplace and easily predictable. Furthermore, such projections could produce an even stronger signal with a far greater angular size. In this study, I present predictions for the lines of sight for such projections through an analysis of the AbacusSummit N-body simulations. I analyzed light cone convergence fields at $z = 2.45$ and searched for clusters of pixels with greater-than-critical convergence. Looking along the line of sight of those clusters, I mapped how the mass of dark matter halos (and mass weighted by the lensing kernel) varies with redshift, which revealed that the origin of the strongest gravitational lenses is typically a limited number of enormous ($10^{14} - 10^{15} M_{\odot}$) halos centered at a particular redshift. Although, a minority can trace their origin to a series of halos spread out across redshift space, which is consistent with a projection along a large-scale structure filament. Finally, I use a sample of luminous red galaxies with photometric redshifts from the Dark Energy Spectroscopic Instrument (DESI) to provide insight into which galaxy clusters may host a filamentary projection.

1. INTRODUCTION

Strong gravitational lensing occurs when light gets bent to such an extreme that multiple images or arcs are produced. The magnification provided by these lenses allows us to probe further into the universe than otherwise possible. Instances of strong lensing can reveal and resolve faint galaxies at $z > 7$ (Wong, et al. 2013), and thus the agents of strong lenses act as ultra deep field telescopes. Furthermore, gravitational lenses have been the most successful tool in the search for dark matter (Massay et al. 2010), as the strength of the magnification is directly connected to the mass distribution of the lens. Even though 0.01% of galaxies are expected to exhibit strong lensing, in 2018, only 300 strong lenses were known (although DESI is expected to double that number)¹. The poor number of lenses has prevented researchers from fully exploiting the benefits offered to us by nature.

The catalog of strong lenses has been limited because there is yet to be a trustworthy method of predicting where they will be. The most extreme lenses are produced when one or multiple galaxy clusters are aligned in the foreground of the source. A naive survey analyst must therefore either encounter strong lenses in the data serendipitously, or turn to a neural network, such as in Storfer et al. (2022). However, the dark matter halos that line the cosmic web can be easily traced through luminous red galaxy (LRG) surveys. Furthermore, a projection along the cosmic web could theoretically expose the source to many multiple lenses along the line of sight, boosting the total power of the lens, while also creating some of the largest lensing cross-sections. This approach therefore promises a method of predicting the largest lenses with the deepest magnification. In particular, a study by Wong et al. (2013) employed the Sloan Digital Sky survey to search for LRG distributions that point toward a series of large dark matter halos aligned along the line of sight (as well as give observational confirmation that LRGs trace large scale structure as expected). The study found that the histogram of LRGs can take on a verity of patterns in redshift space. Specifically, a lens’s mass can be due to either a mass peak centered at a single redshift or multiple structures spread out across redshift space.

¹ Data from the DESI Survey Help Astronomers Count All the Starlight in the Universe.” ScienceDaily, 14 Jan. 2021, <https://www.sciencedaily.com/releases/2021/01/210114085439.htm>.

42 Although, mass alone does not ensure strong lensing, so it would be prudent to more carefully consider the underlying
43 physics. An image lensed at position θ has a Jacobian with the following matrix form.

$$44 \quad \mathcal{A}(\theta) = (1 - \kappa) \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} - \begin{pmatrix} \gamma_1 & \gamma_2 \\ \gamma_2 & -\gamma_1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

45 γ_i is the shear, a parameter responsible for the distortion of the image, and κ is the convergence, a parameter responsible
46 for the magnification of the image (Umetsu 2019)². Therefore, κ is the focus of our attention. In flat space-time, the
47 convergence is a function of the mass density $\delta(\chi, \theta)$, the comoving distance to the lens χ , and the comoving distance
48 to the source χ_s :

$$49 \quad \kappa(\theta) = \frac{3H_0^2\Omega_m}{2c^2} \int d\chi \delta(\chi, \theta) \frac{\chi(\chi_s - \chi)}{\chi_s a} \quad (2)$$

50 where a is the scale factor (Hadzhiyska, et al. 2023). Furthermore, in the thin-lens approximation (in which the large
51 distances involved allow the lens to be approximated as 2 dimensional), the convergence can be defined as a surface
52 density in comparison to the critical surface density Σ_{cr} , the density required to achieve strong lensing.

$$53 \quad \kappa(\theta) = \frac{\Sigma(\theta)}{\Sigma_{cr}}, \quad \Sigma_{cr} = \frac{c^2\chi_s}{4\pi G\chi(\chi_s - \chi)} \quad (3)$$

54 The complexity of the relationships involved in gravitational lensing makes it incredibly difficult to predict the strong
55 lensing sight lines through observational means alone. That is to say that many of the sight lines predicted by Wong
56 et al. (2013) may, in fact, not contain strong lenses. That motivated this study's move to the AbacusSummit N-body
57 simulations.

58
59 AbacusSummit **huge** is an enormous cosmological simulation with half a trillion particles in a box size of $7.5h^{-1}$ Gpc
60 with 33 epochs between $z = 0.1$ and $z = 8$ (Maksimova, et al. 2021). The high accuracy and richness of this simulation
61 allowed for the development of two key data products for this project: light cone convergence fields and light cone halo
62 catalogs. The convergence fields produce a HEALPix map of the sky with NSIDE = 16,384 in which each pixel takes
63 on a κ value for the sight line out to the redshift of that light cone. The halos were identified through the algorithm
64 discussed in (Hadzhiyska et al. 2021). These two data products sketched an outline of my goals. First, I aimed to
65 develop an algorithm to cluster the pixels in the convergence fields in order to determine which sky coordinates would
66 exhibit strong lensing. I then aimed to go into the halo catalogs, look along those coordinates, and attempt to recover
67 the results from Wong et al. (2013).

68
69 Finally, I aim to apply my results to the DESI LRG sample. DESI is a highly multiplexed optical spectrograph that
70 can probe the large scale structure of the universe by taking the spectra of millions of galaxies, including 8 million
71 luminous red galaxies. LRGs are massive, evolved elliptical galaxies whose enormous luminosities $L > 10^{11}L_\odot$ make
72 them an excellent target for DESI. Their morphology is thought to be connected to the fact that they are typically
73 located at the center of galaxy clusters, where they would have had more time to evolve and merge with other galaxies.
74 That property has allowed researchers to empirically confirm that LRGs make excellent biased tracers of the mass
75 distribution of halos in the cosmic web. I will therefore use the DESI LRG sample to identify on-sky galaxy clusters
76 which represent multiple massive halos along the line of sight.

78 2. METHODS AND RESULTS

79 2.1. Clustering the Convergence Fields

80 The light cone chosen for the convergence analysis was taken from `AbacusSummit_huge_c000_ph201`, which has a
81 box size of $L_{\text{box}} = 7500h^{-1}$ Mpc and had a maximum redshift of $z = 2.45$. I designed a custom breadth-first search
82 algorithm—an algorithm that searches a tree data structure for nodes that satisfy a given property. In this case,
83 that property is critical convergence ($\kappa \geq 1$). I initialized the convergence field by finding and selecting all pixels

² Please note that these references are not the provenance of these equations. Instead, they were the sources that oriented my research.

84 with critical convergence, and then giving them the label of being a cluster x_i . For the cluster x_1 , for example, my
 85 algorithm relabels any neighboring clusters as x_1 , and then does the same to those neighbors until no neighboring
 86 clusters remain. Relabeled clusters are then removed from the line of analysis to prevent double counting. The
 87 algorithm ends by outputting average celestial coordinates for each cluster. I ended up with 121,076 clusters, 30,045
 88 of which had more than one pixel. The number of clusters seems to decrease exponentially with cluster size, leaving
 89 only a handful of potentially fruitful coordinates.
 90

Figure 1: A 2.93° by 1.47° section of the Mollweide projection of the convergence field with NSIDE = 16,384. A critical convergence cluster (CC cluster) is marked in red.

Figure 2: A histogram of the pixel cluster sizes for clusters with at least 10 pixels. The maximum was a 52 pixel cluster.

93 2.2. Analyzing the Dark Matter Halos

94 I proceeded with 9 of the largest clusters. In order to convert each pair of celestial coordinates to a sight line, I
 95 took advantage of the fact that the conversion to Cartesian coordinates (which the *huge* simulation uses) requires a
 96 distance parameter:

$$97 \quad x = d \cos(\delta) \cos(\alpha), \quad y = d \cos(\delta) \sin(\alpha), \quad z = d \sin(\delta) \quad (4)$$

98 So, if we define an evenly spaced range of distances out to the edge of the light cone and assign each one to a pair of
 99 celestial coordinates, we produce a line of sight. But, in order to find objects along that sight line, we need to convert
 100 the line into a beam with some width. That is to say that we need to determine a threshold distance along a vector
 101 perpendicular to the line along which we search for halos. Furthermore, this threshold should be minimized, as we only
 102 want to include halos that will produce a multi-arcsecond deflection angle. The maximum radius of the beam should
 103 be approximately equal to the half the angular size of the CC clusters, which, for the largest cluster, corresponds
 104 to a physical size of ~ 2.5 Mpc. The halo catalogs were accessed and analyzed with the NERSC supercomputer at
 105 Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory. Each redshift bin was analyzed one at a time.

106
 107 I ended by weighting the halos by the lensing kernel for a mock source at an arbitrary z_s , which I will select to be
 108 the light cone $z = 2.45$. Doing so will quantify the efficiency of the lens produced by the mass peak. If all photons
 109 come from a constant z , then the lensing kernel is given by

$$110 \quad W^\kappa(z) = \frac{3}{2} \Omega_m H_0^2 \frac{1+z}{H(z)} \frac{\chi(z)}{c} \frac{\chi(z_s) - \chi(z)}{\chi(z_s)} \quad (5)$$

111 This allows for calculations of the lens power spectrum for each of our sight lines (Hadzhiyska, et al. 2018), which could
 112 eventually be compared to known lenses, thereby cross-validating the connections we make between the simulations
 113 and observation.

Figure 3: Halo mass-redshift plots for the 9 sight lines. Each one is annotated with the cluster rank, the total mass of the mass peak, and the total number of sources in the mass peak.

Figure 4: Halo mass-redshift relationships weighted by the lensing kernel. The left plot is the rank 1 cluster (an example of a mass peak lens) and the right plot is the rank 3 cluster (an example of a mass spread lens). The source redshift is set to the lightcone redshift $z = 2.45$.

2.3. Searching for Candidate Lenses with DESI

114

115 The ninth data release of DESI is an enormous achievement in survey cosmology. The catalog contains 2 billion
 116 sources from over 20,000 square degrees of sky (Schlegel et al. 2021). From it, Zhou et al. (2022) were able to produce
 117 a sample of 8 million luminous red galaxies extending out to $z \sim 1$. I extracted a 1,772 square degree subset of that
 118 sample in order to identify candidate hosts for projections along large-scale structure filaments. That is, we want to
 119 find locations where a filamentary lens would occur if there were a source. Given the remarkable halo-tracing abilities
 120 of LRGs, this task is interchangeable with the task of finding on-sky clusters of LRGs that reveal themselves to be
 121 spread out in redshift space. Therefore, I began by transforming my sample into a HEALPix map and running the
 122 same breadth-first search algorithm I used on the convergence fields. With a resolution of $\text{NSIDE} = 2048$, an obvious

123 drop-off in the histogram of LRG counts occurred at pixels with 8 galaxies, so, instead of $\kappa > 1$, the satisfactory
 124 property for this iteration of the algorithm was $N > 8$. However, we must be cautious about using the complete DESI
 125 catalog. Any on-sky regions being reddened by a foreground star could be mistaken as an LRG overdensity. So, I only
 126 included galaxies whose region had been through the pipeline discussed in Zhou et al. (2022), in which a bright star
 127 veto mask was applied to WISE stars—stars from the wide-field infrared survey explorer with $8 < W1 < 8.5$.

Figure 5: A mollweide projection (NSIDE=256) of my DESI LRG subsample after removing galaxies whose region was not processed for WISE stars. The selected region is bounded by RA: $[160^\circ, 220^\circ]$, DEC: $[-10^\circ, 20^\circ]$, and the map is centered on $(190^\circ, 0^\circ)$.

HSC J1156-0038, RA: 179.22077, DEC: -0.6354

No Designation, RA: 197.44628, DEC: -9.65081

ACT-CL J1339.5+1106, RA: 204.89501, DEC: 11.11088

WHL J124726.5+190747, RA: 191.86523, DEC: 19.13526

No Designation, RA: 208.78417, DEC: 17.09430

MOO J1157+1505, RA: 179.450683594, DEC: 15.094787100

ACT-CL J1043.2+0737, RA: 160.81787, DEC: 7.63214

No Designation, RA: 210.47607, DEC: -5.19207

Figure 6: 8 examples of the clusters I analyzed. I give the cluster name (or specify no designation), the coordinates in degrees, a histogram with bin size $z = 0.05$, and provide a 2.75 arcmin image taken from the Legacy Survey viewer.

128 My algorithm identified 25 vast LRG clusters, 11 of which do not have designations in the NASA/IPAC Extragalactic
 129 Database. Visual inspection of the clusters with the Legacy Survey viewer showed that there were no errors in the
 130 identification. I then performed coordinate matches between galaxies in our LRG sample and galaxies in the general
 131 DESI DR9 database in order to assign photometric redshifts. Finally, with the aim of understanding the underlying
 132 halos, I produced redshift histograms of LRG count.

133

3. DISCUSSION

134 The majority of my sight lines (7/9) exhibit an obvious mass peak. Before and after the mass peak, we find only
 135 low mass halos with no obvious redshift consolidation. Around a redshift range no greater than $\Delta z \approx 0.02$, we see
 136 a spike or long, narrow column of massive clusters reaching up to $10^{15} M_{\odot}$. Moreover, while the number halos in
 137 the spike hovers around 10, the total mass of the spike hovers around the mass of the largest halo. That observation
 138 can be combined with the morphology of the peak to conclude that we are mostly finding traditional, non-projection
 139 lenses. However, in the case of sight lines 2 and 3, we find a remarkable mass-spread pattern. In particular, sight line
 140 3 contains no cluster with $M \geq 10^{14} M_{\odot}$. Instead, it actually contains an unusual amount of mid-mass clusters spread
 141 along a $\Delta z \approx 0.2$. Furthermore, while the mass distribution of sight line 2 is less diffuse than 3, it still contains at least
 142 2 dominant peaks. We can conclude that although the majority of strong lenses come from single halo alignments,
 143 it is still absolutely possible to get a multi-halo lens from a filamentary projection. However, while location of the
 144 mass peaks agrees with Wong et al. (2013), which looked through the epochs between $0.1 \leq z \leq 0.7$, it is clear
 145 that I have not fully recovered that study's results. Wong et al. (2013) showed that multi-halo alignments can be
 146 found in roughly equal numbers to single-halo alignments. My novel analysis with the convergence fields implies that
 147 although possible, lenses formed by multi-halo alignments are less likely. Still, as our goal is to increase the catalog
 148 of the largest single lenses, not the total number of lenses, reducing the number of candidates is not entirely undesirable.

149

My work with the DESI LRG sample firstly demonstrates that breadth-first search algorithms acting on pixelated galaxy catalogs is an excellent approach for finding vast LRG clusters. Perhaps my method will be adopted to grow the global catalog of known galaxy clusters. The photometric redshift histograms I produced found a notable amount on-sky clusters whose galaxies are distributed through redshift space. A large scale structure filament has a maximum redshift width of $\Delta z = 0.1$, so, taking HSC J1156-0038 as an example, when we see LRG overdensities at $z = 0.45$ and $z = 0.75$, we may be looking at a mass-spread lens. Follow-up observations of those clusters with spectroscopic redshifts are needed to determine this definitively. That brings me to the most important future step for this project: getting spectroscopic redshifts for my galaxy clusters. Photometric redshifts are generally unreliable. Not only are they susceptible to reddening, but they are less precise and can have errors of a few percent, which would strongly affect our results on the small Δz scales we are considering. If future researchers do move to spectroscopic redshifts, the increased precision would give them the ability to correlate LRG count and mass, which would be the ideal method for flushing out strong lenses.

There are a couple ways to do this. Firstly, one could map the extent of each halo, producing scale radii. Then, since central LRGs follow a Navarro–Frenk–White (NFW) density profile, a total halo mass can be produced. However, it has been recently revealed that the correlation between LRGs and dark matter halos is not a straight forward as previously thought. Many LRGs are simply the center of their own sub-halo, and therefore the brightest galaxies may not be at the center of the overall halo, nor would the most massive halos always have an LRG at their center. So, in some circumstances, LRGs in fact not tracing NFW distributions (Hoshino et al. 2018.) Alternatively, one could consider the stellar mass/halo mass relation (SHMR). The SHMR exhibits a peak efficiency at a certain halo mass such that galaxies within halos of that mass convert the highest fraction of their available baryonic matter into stars. Above and below this peak mass, the efficiency of converting baryons into stars decreases, often attributed to various feedback processes that inhibit star formation (Wechsler, et al. 2018). That relationship can be determined empirically and then used to connect LRGs to halo masses. Finally, one can exploit the relationship between a dark matter halo’s intrinsic 3D velocity dispersion and the line-of-sight velocity dispersion deduced from satellite galaxies. There exists a window in the line of sight velocity from which mass can be accurately deduced (Elahi et al. 2018).

To end, I discuss the potential uses of the strong lenses that could be found using my results. One of the key goals of modern cosmology is to constrain cosmological parameters, and strong lenses actually provide opportunities to do so. As one example, the Hubble constant H_0 directly affects angular diameter distances. So, if a supernova happens to be lensed into multiple images, such as an Einstein cross, it is possible to look for time delays in the supernova’s magnitude fluctuations. Those would be determined by changes in length of the light path, and hence the time delays would be probing the distances involved in the lens (Birrer et al. 2021). This technique requires a very good understanding of the lensing setup, and thus hinges directly on studies such as this one. Furthermore, increasing the number of known strong lenses of course also increases the occurrences of lensed supernovae being observed. Next, the high redshifts involved in cosmic web lensing may also allow for the same approach to be applied to fluctuations in lensed quasars. Angular diameter distances are also highly sensitive to Ω_m and Ω_Λ , and studies such as Cao et al. (2012) have demonstrated that it is possible to constrain those parameters through analysis of arcs, which constrain the projected mass of the lens. Strong lenses can also be used to resolve faint, ultra high redshift galaxies that would otherwise go unnoticed or would require massive exposure times from expensive deep field observatories like JWST. Shu et al. (2022) was able to find 277 candidates of strongly lensed faint galaxies—a number this study aims to majorly boost—and were actually able to take spectra, demonstrating the exciting potential of these lenses.

4. SUPPLEMENTARY RESULTS

It’s worth noting that beam radius in my halo analysis was larger than the virial radius of some halos. However, it can be demonstrated that we still achieve multi-arcsecond deflection angles for an impact parameter of 2.5 Mpc (my largest beam width). Assuming a NFW density profile, we can get the deflection angle via

$$\hat{\alpha}(R) = \frac{4G}{c^2} \int d\xi' \frac{(\xi - \xi')\Sigma(\xi')}{|\xi - \xi'|^2}, \quad \Sigma(R) = \Omega_m \rho_{\text{crit}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dz \rho(\sqrt{R^2 + z^2}) \quad (6)$$

Figure 7: Deflection angle as a function of impact parameter for a variety of halo masses.

197 Although, even if we achieve large deflection angles, the size of my beam radius is still a major shortcoming of this
 198 study, and ideally it should be further minimized. I recommend that future research move to a more adaptive beam
 199 size, and that further consideration be put into the determination of that size.

200

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205

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